

6Enhanced Intersection Particle Swarm Optimization (EIPSO) Algorithm and Image Processing Techniques for Lung Cancer Detection

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Abstract: Image processing techniques are now broadly used in several medical sectors for primary identification and therapy phases. Pre-processing, extraction of features, and segmentation strategies like thresholding or K-means clustering are deliberated as part of the dispensation processes.. By using picture improvement and segmentation algorithms in MATLAB software, the goal is to obtain more accurate findings. CT used to detect lung cancer is one of the most accepted imaging techniques in medicine. We proposed a method for identifying lung cancer based on different pertinent techniques and picture segmentation, one of the intermediate phases in image processing. The goal is to create a quick image segmentation technique for medical imaging, which will decrease how frequently clinicians examine computer tomography (CT) scan images to look for lung cancer.. Large images formed by current medical imaging technologies are mainly difficult to estimate and improve manually. This is worrisome because of its importance in efficiently detecting and starting therapy effectively. Recent image processing techniques are very important to study as they are frequently used in a variety of medical issues.

To extract the tumour from the lung picture in this study, we applied and assessed the performance of optimization techniques such as k-means clustering, the optimization of particle swarms, and the enhanced intersecting particle swarm optimization technique (EIPSO).. After reviewing the outcomes of the median, adaptive median, and average filters in the first preliminary step, it was determined that the adaptive median filter was the most suitable for usage with medical CT scans. Based on the outcomes of our studies, we concluded that our method was effective. The preprocessed image with good quality is susceptible to multiple algorithms in studies using 20 lung scans as samples, with the EIPSO technique having the best accuracy (96.19%).

Keyword: Artificial intelligence, Optimization, Algorithm, Image processing, Lung cancer, Optimization

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Introduction

1.1 Lung cancer: One of the deadliest diseases is cancer [4]. This malignant growth in the lung tissue exhibits unchecked cell proliferation. According to data from the Global Burden of Cancer, 14.1 million people worldwide had cancer in 2012.. Lung cancer: One of the deadliest diseases is cancer [4]. This malignant growth in the lung tissue exhibits unchecked cell proliferation. According to Global Burden of Cancer data, 14.1 million people worldwide had cancer in 2012. [5]. Small cell lung cancer (SCLC) The two primary subtypes of lung cancer are and non-small cell lung cancers (NSCLC). 85% of instances of lung cancer are NSCLC, naturally detected in smokers [6, 7]. Lung cancer is also more expected among women whose husbands smoke (between 10 and 15 per cent of nonsmokers develop the disease) [9] and is also brought on by asbestos, radon gas, second-hand smoke, air pollution, and other factors.

The traditional methods for identifying the presence of lung cancer include computed tomography (CT) and X-rays. Typically, a CT scan or bronchoscopy-based biopsy is used to confirm the diagnosis. The leading cause of cancer-related death among men is lung cancer. Therefore, it's critical to grow new, reliable techniques for early lung cancer detection [10]. In prior work, lung cancer was examined utilizing microarray data clustering methods [11] and conventional image processing techniques on CT scan data to accurately and successfully identify lung cancer [12].. Early prediction of lung cancer can rise patient survival utilizing imaging methods like computed tomography (CT), which results in greater image quality and outcomes. Going forward, new evolutionary algorithms need to be researched and implemented to solve problems related to medical image segmentation. We proposed and evaluated a different picture segmentation approach for algorithmic lung cancer analysis in this study. To do the study, 20 lung imaging samples and a few algorithms were obtained. A combination of algorithms based on Adaptive Median filtering, and Enhanced Intersection Particle Swarm Optimization (EIPSO), among others, has provided more accurate results. Figure 3, shown below, outlines a The system for identifying the presence of lung cancer uses four fundamental stages. Obtaining CT imaging data is the initial stage. Image processing is used in the second stage to enhance image quality. Image segmentation, the third phase, is crucial for finding cancer. The fourth stage is feature extraction, which provides a conclusion about the presence or absence of lung cancer.

This study aims to seamlessly and rapidly detect lung cancer by leveraging the effectiveness of adaptive media filtering, thresholding, k-means clustering, and particle swarm optimization to develop an enhanced EIPSOE algorithm. We were also able to achieve better spatial processing with the kernal size without replacing pixel values with median values. This study is organized as follows.

Section 1 contains the introduction, and Section 2 has includes related work. The suggested strategy is presented in Section 3, and the outcomes are shown in Section 4. Conclusions and recommendations for the future are given in Section 5.

2. Related works

To conduct substantial studies in lung cancer/imaging recognition systems, scientists have recently used techniques and approaches focused on image acquisition, segmentation/analysis, and detection utilizing models (which may be formulas) or artificial neural networks. The authors of "Detection of Lung Cancer Using Image Processing Techniques" [13] used image development and binarization techniques to describe tumour extraction based on various segmentation outlines and several algorithms. Though, due to watershed segmentation, the extraction of tumour mechanisms desires to be more accurate. In the work "Detection of Lung Cancer by Evolutionary Detection" by K. Senthil Kumar and K. Venkatlaxami, we found Image segmentation algorithms are developed for various medical pictures using K-means clustering, K-median clustering, swarms optimization of elements, and inertial approaches. The results demonstrated that the adaptive median filter outperformed the median and mean filters. Many medical areas have used imaging methods to recover detection and pre-treatment steps. At this

stage, the elapsed time is an important factor detecting the patient's illness as early as possible. This is shown in the book "Detection and Classification of Lung Tumors Using K-Means Clustering" by P.B. Sangamitraa and S. Govindaraju.

In "Segmentation and Classification of Lung Tumors from 3D CT Images Using K-Means Clustering," Prionjit Sarkar and Zakir Hussain used 3D CT images to pinpoint the precise location and size of tumours. Consequences show how to manage these problems by utilizing the neighbourhood and connectivity qualities in CT image pixels. Concerning the diagnostic technique used, it has been found that the time limit issue with CT in forecasting the presence of lung cancer is unclear. Image processing, segmentation, and feature extraction techniques were thoroughly covered in the article "Detection of lung cancer in her CT images using image processing" by Anita Chaudhary and SonitSukhraj Singh. In the study "Detection and Diagnosis of Lung Tumors in CT Imaging" by Amutha and Wahidabanu, segmentation was done utilising histogram-based feature extraction and nonlocal denoising for preprocessing. Educations reveal that shorter lung fields can be divided using this technique in various pathologies. In their paper "Lung Cancer Detection in CT Images Using Image Processing," researchers Nidhi S. Nadkarni and SangamBorkar employed median filtering for picture preprocessing and quantitative morphological procedures for image segmentation. Then, the characteristics of that area of interest were discovered. Several studies have also been conducted based on using artificial neural networks (ANNs) for discrimination, recognition, or comparison. ZhihuaZhou used her ensemble of artificial neural networks in her work "Lung Cancer Cell Identification Based on Artificial Neural Networks.". This is a grasping paradigm where many artificial neural networks are combined to address issues. NED is a suggested diagnostic technique that employs ANNs to identify lung cancer cells in images of needle samples collected from the body of a patient diagnosed with the disease.

Additionally, in a study by Moffy Vyas and Amita Dessai titled "Lung Cancer Detection System Using Lung CT Imaging," radiologists used CT scans to find and monitor cancer progression in the body. It demonstrated how to partition lung regions of interest using mathematical morphological operations as part of a lung cancer detection system. There, Haralick traits were taken out and used by ANN to categorize cancer. WasudeoRahane, and HimaliDalvi, in their work, "Lung Cancer Detection Using Image Processing and Machine Learning", affirmed that SVM is an efficient method for lung cancer detection by any other methods. Only abnormal images were used for segmentation, and the tumor was detected using segmentation.

In conclusion, [14] used categorization methods for lung cancer diagnosis, including Naive Bayes, SVM, choice trees, and logistic regression. The outcomes show that, among all algorithms, the Decision Tree was found to have provided the highest accuracy.

3. Proposed approach

3.1 Image Acquisitions

The right preprocessing, filtering, image segmentation, and extraction procedures are used to detect lung cancer. Below are further specifics on these ideas and strategies. Examples of CT scan image data of (a) lungs infected with COVID-19 and (b) lungs infected with pneumonia are shown in Figure 2. The pictures accurately demonstrate how

the lungs look under specified circumstances.

Figure 2: Computed tomography (CT) slices of lung in axial view

The images utilized come from the database of CT scans. Our information is sourced from the public access VIA and ELCAP databases [5]. The subsequent phases, depicted in Figure 3 below, are part of the operating method and process flow.

1. Preprocessing
2. Filtering
3. Threshold
4. Image division
5. Feature of extraction
6. Detection of tumors

Figure 3: Procedure flow diagram of the projected method

3.2 Preprocessing

The image enhancement stage is the first step in the image preprocessing stage. The viewer's impression of the image is improved via image enhancement technology—approaches for enhancing images in the spatial and frequency

domains. methods are also used to provide suitable inputs for automatic image processing techniques. Image improvement techniques used in image processing include Median filtering, dynamic filtering, thresholding, and others. Recently, other methods for improving images include morphological editing, intensity matching, and binarization.

3.2.1 filters for the adaptive median and median. A median filter keeps the image's clarity while reducing noise. The average of its neighboring pixels replaces each pixel, as the name suggests. With this filter, a 3 3 window is used. [15]. The process for building the median filter is provided in Algorithm 1, and it is one of the best conventional filters for reducing speckle noise. A significant part is played by spatial processing that uses adaptive median filtering to preserve edge details and eliminate non-impulse noise. The edges and fine features of the image are preserved using the adaptive median filter. Each pixel has a different window size for the adaptable median filter.

MEDIAN MEDIAN ALGORITHM

- (1) Assume that "A" is an M by N input matrix.
- (2) To create an $M + 2$ -by- $N + 2$ matrices, zeroes must be added to the edges of the input matrix.
- (3) Grab a 3x3-inch mask.
- (4) Attach the mask to the matrix 'A''s first element, represented by its first row and column.
- (5) Choose every item in the mask's list, then sort them in ascending order.
- (6) Substitute the median (central element) from the sorted array for element $A(1, 1)$.
- (7) Transfer the mask to the next item.
- (8) Repeat steps 4 through 7 until each matrix "A" component has an associated median.

3.2.2. Average filter.

The dimensional noise in digital photographs is eliminated using this clear filter. This noise is primarily a result of the data-gathering procedure. Each pixel's neighbourhood average is calculated, and the appropriate standard is used. This technique is performed for each pixel in the image [15]]. By moving the operator over the pixel region, every pixel in the digital image can be modified. The mean filtering procedure is shown in the following algorithm, Algorithm 2.

ALGORITHM 2: Average filter

- (1) Assume that "A" is an M by N input matrix.
- (2) To create an $M + 2$ -by- $N + 2$ matrices, zeroes must be added to the edges of the input matrix. (3) Grab a 3x3-inch mask.
- (4) Set the mask over the initial component. H. The component is in the matrix 'A' row 1, column 1.
- (5) Pick every item the mask lists, then calculate the average.
- (6) Substitute the median for the $A(1, 1)$ element by obtaining it from the sorted array.
- (7) Move the mask to the following object. (8) Keep going back to steps 4 through 7 until each element of the matrix "A" has a corresponding median.

3.2.3. Threshold approach:

Thresholding is the most beneficial technique for segmenting images because it aids in determining the segmentation threshold. There are several purposes for points, such as providing tight areas for storage and usability. Thresholding for medical image segmentation is slower than other segmentation techniques. Thresholding approaches have received attention in the past 10 to 15 years [7]. Thresholding turns a grayscale image into a binary image with two levels per pixel. This paper discovers a global image threshold for lung image segmentation using Otsu's thresholding.

Table 1: SSI and SMPI values of input images

Sample Images	SSI		SMPI	
	Median Filter	Adaptive median filter	Median Filter	Adaptive median filter
Image 1	0.8308	0.8186	0.9888	0.9138
Image 2	0.8332	0.8287	0.9690	0.9352
Image 3	0.8309	0.8191	0.9399	0.9496
Image 4	0.8180	0.7737	0.9236	0.9203
Image 5	0.8320	0.8178	0.9633	0.9406
Image 6	0.8318	0.7600	0.9375	0.9657
Image 7	0.8302	0.8367	0.9708	0.9564
Image 8	0.8365	0.8254	0.9222	0.9893
Image 9	0.8372	0.8341	0.9116	0.9376
Image 10	0.8438	0.8212	0.9704	0.9159
Image 11	0.8331	0.7422	0.9488	0.9843
Image 12	0.8189	0.8252	0.9326	0.9421
Image 13	0.7339	0.8435	0.9282	0.9274
Image 14	0.8542	0.8598	0.9967	0.9848
Image 15	0.8108	0.8284	0.9685	0.9336
Image 16	0.8342	0.8195	0.9355	0.9513
Image 17	0.8639	0.8452	0.9870	0.9482
Image 18	0.7883	0.7957	0.9208	0.9196
Image 19	0.8120	0.7784	0.9438	0.9206
Image 20	0.8285	0.7590	0.9541	0.9432

3.3 Segmenting images

Image segmentation is a technique that separates an image into parts and labels each pixel to make the pixels with the same label share a common visual trait. Segmentation alters how the image is perceived and makes scrutiny easier. Colour image segmentation can also be used for tissue measurement and classification. The image segmentation process produces the same lung ROIs, each distinct. K-means clustering is used for segmentation in colour-based segmentation.

3.3.1. K-means clustering:

This straightforward approach reduces the sum of the squared distances to the cluster centers by grouping a given sample into the appropriate number of clusters. The mistake is minimized because there is no squaring operation in this algorithm. Some of its weaknesses are that it randomly selects K samples. As a result, it depends on the value of K, etc. Here, the first grouping can recognize or determine clusters meaningfully because the number of data is not significant. The most straightforward The k-means clustering technique is the most straightforward and practical approach to cluster analysis. This program creates two or more clusters from a given dataset [16]. The selected cluster centres will have no bearing on how accurate this strategy is. The best cluster centres must be chosen if you want good results. The Euclidean distance is a typical method for dividing up data sets [17]. Based on their Euclidean distance, pixels are grouped into a single cluster. Another clustering strategy that slightly modifies the The K-median algorithm for clustering is known as k-means. The k-means clustering procedure is described in the following Algorithm 3.

(1) Pick the cluster's center. Call her "C" for short.

Find the Euclidean distance in step two.

(3) If the Euclidean distance between the clusters and the pixels is small, each pixel is given to the proper cluster.

(4) Re-calculate the new cluster centres using the following formula after all pixels have been separated:

(5) Continue performing steps 2 through 4 until a predetermined number of conditions have been satisfied.

ALGORITHM 3: k-Means clustering

Table 2: Statistical results from the k-means algorithm

Images	True +ve rate	True -ve rate	False +ve rate	False -ve rate	Accuracy
Image 1	86.8774	89.1223	10.8456	11.1234	87.5990
Image 2	84.6522	89.5456	10.4785	13.3345	88.2689
Image 3	82.8945	87.3542	12.6210	16.1456	85.7578
Image 4	81.6532	85.7097	14.2234	17.3567	84.2167
Image 5	82.5671	84.2218	15.7456	16.4678	83.9256
Image 6	81.7243	82.4673	17.5567	17.2789	82.5745
Image 7	82.1872	79.0784	20.9678	18.8890	80.1534
Image 8	81.2551	77.7347	22.2890	19.7089	78.0634
Image 9	82.7845	78.4942	21.5098	18.2897	80.1623
Image 10	81.4324	77.4216	22.5987	19.5687	79.0312
Image 11	82.7743	78.0482	21.9876	18.2576	79.9712
Image 12	85.0765	78.8555	21.1765	15.9465	81.5223
Image 13	80.6155	78.7872	21.2654	18.3354	80.2834
Image 14	78.8971	78.6217	20.3543	20.1243	79.3045
Image 15	81.9032	78.4675	21.5234	19.0243	79.7656
Image 16	84.1267	78.1328	21.8345	18.8132	77.2156
Image 17	81.1240	78.1671	21.8587	19.8807	79.2267
Image 18	77.2572	83.5893	16.4896	21.7386	80.7078
Image 19	76.7032	83.7345	16.2347	21.2142	81.0889
Image 20	77.7128	84.3123	15.6916	22.2111	80.2469

Particle swarm optimization, section 3.3.2.

PSO is a high-level, algorithmic framework successfully applied to interpreting medical images [18]. It imitates foraging birds' social behaviour [19]. Sharing and transmitting information is the fundamental tenet of PSO. Each particle in this method has an early place and velocity. Speed-based suitability score, where n is the number of clusters. Algorithm 4 below details the particle swarm optimization process.

(1) Set the particles' locations and velocities to random values.

2. Create a fitness activity.

(3) Establish the fitness value for each particle.

Compare the value of fitness to the highest level of fitness. If the values for fitness are higher, create a new plot using the current value.

(5) For each particle, repeat steps 3 through 5.

Updating the velocity using equation (1) in step six

(7) Enhance the role.

(8) Gbest Update

(9) Continue performing steps 7 through 9 until specific conditions are met or for the specified number of iterations.

ALGORITHM 4: Particle swarm optimization [18, 20]

Table 3: Statistical results from the PSO algorithm

Images	True +ve rate	True -ve rate	False +ve rate	False -ve rate	Accuracy
Image 1	87.8783	89.1554	10.8446	12.1217	88.5937
Image 2	86.6527	89.5874	10.4126	13.3473	88.2682
Image 3	83.8975	87.3900	12.6100	16.1025	85.7501
Image 4	82.6502	85.7011	14.2989	17.3498	84.2186
Image 5	83.5680	84.2582	15.7418	16.4320	83.9216
Image 6	82.7250	82.4643	17.5654	17.2750	82.5795
Image 7	81.1893	79.0554	20.9446	18.8107	80.1519
Image 8	80.2543	77.7549	22.2451	19.7457	82.0656
Image 9	81.7874	78.4139	21.5861	18.2126	80.1606
Image 10	80.4304	77.4794	22.5206	19.5696	82.0378
Image 11	81.7725	78.0352	21.9648	18.2275	83.9755
Image 12	84.0795	78.8912	21.1088	15.9205	81.5222
Image 13	81.6145	78.7989	21.2011	18.3855	80.2845
Image 14	79.8951	78.6152	21.3848	20.1049	85.3067
Image 15	80.9012	78.4626	21.5374	19.0988	82.7643
Image 16	80.1249	78.1480	21.8520	18.8751	86.2175
Image 17	80.1220	78.1687	21.8318	19.8780	80.2298
Image 18	78.2509	83.5148	16.4852	21.7491	80.7080
Image 19	78.7041	83.7431	16.2569	21.2959	81.0870
Image 20	76.7118	84.3245	15.6755	23.2882	80.1851

3.3.3. At the moment, Enhanced Intersection Particle Swarm Optimization (EIPSO) is concentrating on new particles that validate the best location in this region. The velocity update equation for this new particle, considered a swarm member in this work, is [21]. In some benchmark tests, EIPSO demonstrated exceptional performance while unimodally arranging the fewest particles in the smallest space. Algorithm 5 below outlines the procedures involved in EIPSO. (1) Set the number of clusters and iterations to their initial values.

(2) Setup p , sc , fc , and num . Success is equal to 0, and the number of failures is also equal to 0.

(3) Establish an exercise function. Clustering

(4) Calculate each particle's fitness value. (5) Update the current locally optimal response. (6) Continue to carry out steps 4 and 5 for the required number of times.

(7) For the current global best particle choice step, update each particle's position and velocity.

(8) Put the selection operator into action

(9) Run the clustering procedure if the local best position has altered in any way. If not, halt the algorithm.

ALGORITHM 5: EIPSO algorithm

Table 4: Statistical results from the EIPSO algorithm

Images	True +ve rate	True -ve rate	False +ve rate	False -ve rate	Accuracy
Image 1	91.6158	98.9999	0.002	9.1217	90.6937
Image 2	90.9563	98.9999	0.002	13.3473	92.3682
Image 3	88.8404	98.9999	0.002	16.1025	91.8601
Image 4	87.2946	98.9999	0.002	11.3498	96.3286
Image 5	87.3583	98.9999	0.002	16.4320	90.8316
Image 6	86.1567	98.9999	0.002	17.2750	93.6895
Image 7	83.4867	98.9999	0.002	16.8107	94.2619
Image 8	83.1082	98.9999	0.002	14.7457	91.1756
Image 9	81.7874	98.9999	0.002	16.2126	90.2706
Image 10	80.4304	98.9999	0.002	12.5696	96.1478
Image 11	81.7725	98.9999	0.002	15.2275	92.8855
Image 12	84.0795	98.9999	0.002	15.9205	95.5238
Image 13	81.6145	98.9999	0.002	13.3855	93.2806
Image 14	89.8951	98.9999	0.002	14.1049	91.3023
Image 15	80.9012	98.9999	0.002	15.0988	94.7600
Image 16	80.1249	98.9999	0.002	16.8751	90.2121
Image 17	80.1220	98.9999	0.002	17.8780	95.2229
Image 18	82.2509	98.9999	0.002	15.7491	92.7020
Image 19	81.7041	98.9999	0.002	11.2959	96.0816
Image 20	86.7118	98.9999	0.002	13.2882	93.1831

The comparative results of the different segmentation approaches were presented in table 5 below to find out the degree of performance and hence the accuracy of the reviewed methods.

Table 5: Statistical Comparative results of Accuracy

Images	K-means	PSO	EIPSO
Image 1	87.5990	88.5937	90.6937
Image 2	88.2689	88.2682	92.3682
Image 3	85.7578	85.7501	91.8601
Image 4	84.2167	84.2186	96.3286
Image 5	83.9256	83.9216	90.8316
Image 6	82.5745	82.5795	93.6895
Image 7	80.1534	80.1519	94.2619
Image 8	78.0634	82.0656	91.1756
Image 9	80.1623	80.1606	90.2706
Image 10	79.0312	82.0378	96.1478
Image 11	79.9712	83.9755	92.8855
Image 12	81.5223	81.5222	95.5238
Image 13	80.2834	80.2845	93.2806
Image 14	79.3045	85.3067	91.3023

Image 15	79.7656	82.7643	94.7600
Image 16	77.2156	86.2175	90.2121
Image 17	79.2267	80.2298	95.2229
Image 18	80.7078	80.7080	92.7020
Image 19	81.0889	81.0870	96.0816
Image 20	80.2469	80.1851	93.1831

3.4 Feature extraction:

The image feature extraction phase is the key phase where algorithms are used to predict and delineate various portions of the picture. Utilizing feature extraction also reduces the dimensionality. Two techniques are used to assess the likelihood of lung cancer: binarization and masking.

Its fundamental attributes include, for instance:

1. The region that displays the pixel count.
2. Skewness is a symmetry indicator.
3. Equidistant conditions the same size as the ROI
4. Contrast: This metric assesses the degree of contrast between a pixel and its surrounding pixels.
5. Convex portion: It provides information such as the number of pixels in a convex image.

Kurtosis: the pattern of a random variable's probability distribution

7. Energy is the total of the GLCM's squared components.

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Kurtosis: the pattern of a random variable's probability distribution

7. Energy is the total of the GLCM's squared components.

The proposed system's objective is toTable 6: Values of Features

	Lung 1	Lung 2	Lung 3	Lung 4	Lung 5
Energy	1	1	0.831	1	0.765
Smoothness	1	1	1	1	1
Contrast	0	0	1.650	0	3.400
Mean	4071	4071	4071	4071	4071
Skewness	5.352	4.464	4.472	4.549	4.885
Kurtosis	32.763	22.298	23.619	23.517	29.089
Variance	3.179e+08	2.365e+08	2.054e+08	2,391e+08	2.058e+08

4. Results/Discussions

The methods and procedures used in this study were technically implemented in MATLAB coding, and the equivalent results were authenticated. In the preprocessing phase, median filter and adaptive median performances were

compared. SSI and SMPI values are provided in Table 1, and the results suggest that the adaptive median filter has more essential qualities than the average filters for medical picture segmentation.

K-means clustering reduces artefacts, as perfect results cannot be obtained after thresholding. This is so because bone defects and other abnormalities in the lung are often present as lung tumors. Figures 4 show normal lung image under CT while figure 6 show the tumour area extracted from the lung image.

The outcomes of the PSO-based segmentation method are shown in Table 3, while the k-means clustering segmentation technique results are shown in Table 2. Table 4 displays the EIPSO segmentation algorithm, and Table 5 compares the

algorithms' degrees of accuracy.

Figure 4: Normal CT lung image

Figure 5: CT Lung image after thresholding

Figure 6: Extracted Tumor

Figure 5 above displays the final images following the EIPSO algorithm's segmentation.

Earlier studies used techniques including Lung cancer diagnosis using PSO, evolutionary optimization, and the algorithm for SVM with the filter Gabor. The accuracy of this approach was 89.5% [22], compared to 90% [23] for the K-NN classification process utilizing the genetic algorithm. The created EIPSO algorithm provided an accuracy of 96.19%, and Table 7 compares the results with various approaches already in use.

5. Conclusion

This study discovered effective methods for identifying lung cancer, K-means clustering and thresholding. This is because lung cancers have groups of cells, and K-means clustering is used to detect groups in images effectively. Similar to thresholding, it has been found that setting a threshold effectively performs image processing. The suggested proposed method has greater tumour extraction accuracy when compared to all other methods. Given that CT pictures have better image quality than MRI and X-rays, they may be said to be the most effective for detecting lung

cancer. Finally, different optimization algorithms for tumour detection were evaluated. Medical images usually need to be preprocessed before performing statistical experiments. Due to the adaptive median filter's lower speckle suppressing index and speckle and average conservation index values, it performs better than the median and average filters. Comparing the algorithms used, the accuracy of tumour extraction using the developed combined method EIPSO gave the highest accuracy of 96.19%, achieving over 90% accuracy for all pictures. Compared to the earlier method's 90% accuracy, this one is more precise.

We intend to employ more optimization methods to increase accuracy in our future work, which can also detect lung tumours' size and location utilizing cutting-edge machine learning concepts like CNN and PNN.

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Data Availability

On reasonable request, the CT imaging data used to support the study's findings are made public.

Conflicts of Interest

On reasonable request, the CT imaging data used to support the study's findings are made public.

References

1. Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer, Available at: <http://www.katemacintyrefoundation.org/pdf/non-small-cell.pdf>, Adapted from National Cancer Institute (NCI) and Patients Living with Cancer (PLWC), 2007, (accessed July 2011).
2. Levner I., Zhang H., "Classification-Driven Watershed Segmentation", IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, 2007, 16(5), 1437-45.
3. D. Lin and C. Yan, "Lung nodules identification rules extraction with neural fuzzy network", IEEE, Neural Information Processing, vol. 4,(2002).
4. [1] Permata T S and Bustamam A 2015 Clustering protein-protein interaction network of TP53 tumor suppressor protein using Markov clustering algorithm International Conference on Advanced Computer Science and Information Systems (ICACSIS) pp 221–226
5. [2] GLOBOCAN 2012, International Agency for Research on Cancer, World Health Organization. <http://globocan.iarc.fr/>
6. D. Sharma and G. Jindal, "Identifying Lung Cancer Using Image Processing Techniques," International Conference on Computational Techniques and Artificial Intelligence (ICCTAf'2011), 2011, pp. 115-120
7. Md. Badrul Alam, Miah Mohammad Abu Yousuf, "Detection of Lung Cancer from CT Image Using Image Processing and Neural Network" 2nd Int'l Conf on Electrical Engineering and Information & Communication Technology (ICEEICT) 20 IS Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka-1342, Bangladesh, 21-23 May 2015.
8. Levner I., Zhang H., Classification-Driven Watershed Segmentation, IEEE Transactions on Image Processing, 2007, 16(5), 1437-45.

9. RachidSammouda, Jamal Abu Hassan, Mohamed Sammouda, Abdulridha Al-Zuhairy, HatemabouElAbbas, "Computer Aided Diagnosis System for Early Detection of Lung Cancer Using Chest Computer Tomography Images", GVIP 05 Conference, 19-21 December 2005, CICC, Cairo, Egypt.
10. B. Rani, A. K. Goel, and R. Kaur, "A modified approach for lung cancer detection using bacterial foraging optimization algorithm," *International Journal of Scientific Research Engineering and Technology*, vol. 5, no. 1, 2016.
11. Khalid R 2014 Clustering analysis of cancerous microarray data *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research* 6(9) pp 488-493, ISSN: 0975-7384
12. [4] Kajal N et al 2015 Early Detection of Lung Cancer Using Image Processing Technique: Review *International Journal of Advent Research in Computer and Electronics (IJARCE)* 2(2), E-ISSN: 2348-5523.
13. Mokhled S-Altarawaneh," Lung cancer Detection Using Image Processing Techniques", *Leonardo Electronic Journal of Practice and Technologies*, Issue 20, January-June 2012.
14. Radhika P.R, Rakhi A.S Nair, Veena G " A Comparative study of lung cancer detection using machine learning algorithms", 2019
15. G. Gupta, "Algorithm for image processing using improved median filter and comparison of mean, median and improved median filter," *International Journal of Soft Computing and m Engineering*, vol. 1, no. 5, 2011.
16. K. Venkatalakshmi and S. M. Shalinie, "Classification of multispectral images using support vector machines based on PSO and K-means clustering," in *Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Sensing and Information Processing*, pp. 127–133, Melbourne, VIC, Australia, December 2005.
17. K. Venkatalakshmi and S. M. Shalinie, "Multispectral image classification using modified k-means clustering," *International Journal on Neural and Mass-Parallel Computing and Information Systems*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 113–120, 2007.
18. K. Senthilkumar, K. Venkatalakshmi, K. Karthikeyan, and P. Kathirkamasundari, "An efficient method for segmenting digital image using a hybrid model of particle swarm optimization and artificial bee colony algorithm," *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, vol. 10, pp. 444–449, 2015.
19. K. Venkatalakshmi and S. Mercyshalinie, "Classification of multispectral images using support vector machines based on PSO and k-means clustering," in *Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Sensing and Information Processing*, pp. 127–133, Bangalore, India, December 2005
20. K. Venkatalakshmi, P. AnishaPraisyy, R. Maragathavalli, and S. Mercyshalinie, "A customized particle swarm optimization for classification of multispectral imagery based on feature fusion," *International Arab Journal of Information Technology*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 327–333, 2008.
21. P. K. Patel, V. Sharma, and K. Gupta, "Guaranteed convergence particle swarm optimization using Personal Best," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 73, no. 7, pp. 6–10, 2013
22. A. Asuntha, N. Singh, and A. Srinivasan, "PSO, genetic optimization and SVM algorithm used for lung cancer detection," *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 351–359, 2016.
23. P. Bhuvanewari and A. Brintha +ereese, "Detection of cancerin lung with K-NN classification using genetic algorithm," *International Conference on Nanomaterials and Technologies*, vol. 10, pp. 433–440, 2014.

